

Attributes of interpersonal trust in Virtual Learning Environments

Traceability of the attributes identified in the articles.

Table 2
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Attribute that influences interpersonal trust	Article	Attribute that influences interpersonal trust	Article
Authentic emotional communication	A44	Honesty	A30, A34
Collaboration	A16, A28		
Collaborative communication	A27	Hasty to conclusions	A10
Common interests / Similar interests, tastes and preferences	A30, A42	Keeping promises and commitments	A10
		Leadership	A20
Cooperation / Mutual cooperation	A10, A13, A30	Low Grades	A46
Credibility	A11, A26	Not taking responsibility	A10
Dedication	A32	Perceived trustworthiness of the partner	A13
Direct experience (Past interact)	A46	Perform activities	A21
Discussions in forums	A7	Predictability	A41
Does not assume error	A10	Previous experience (Past interaction)	A30
Effective communication	A32	Previous interaction (Past interaction)	A14
Effort	A32		
Egocentrism	A10	Recommendation	A28, A30
Ethics	A23	Reputation	A5, A6, A8, A28, A38, A46
Experience of friends of his friends	A30	Similarity among users	A39
Feedback / Feedback in interactions	A14, A30, A45, A46	Sincerity	A32
Friendliness	A1	Socio-emotional interaction	A23
Friends in common	A22, A42		
High knowledge on a given topic	A46	Elapsed time	A9, A28, A30
Higher Grades	A18, A46	Use of symbols and avatars	A3
Honest communication	A10		